

APPENDICE - IL TRITONO E LE MUSICHE DI TRADIZIONE: UNA CARATTERIZZAZIONE TEORICA SUL CENTRO SUD ITALIA - Claudio Merico

Fig.1

A MONTASOLA

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8

A MONTASOLAC'E E - E DI PIANTE UNFIORRE MONT -

9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16

-TASCINAE- E E L'ARO - RÈMI - 0 - 0

17 18 19 20 21 22 23 24

MONTASOLI - NA E = E - E - E - E

(p) (p) (p) (p) (p)

25 26 27 28 29 30 31 32

E - E - E - E L'ARO - RÈMI 10 - 0 - 0

(p) (p) (p) (p) (p)

33 34 35 36 37 38 39 40

- 0

fig.2

BELLA FIGLIOLA CA
VENI CO MEA

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8

III V IV# I V

BE - LA - A FI - I - GHO - LA CHE - È VE - NI CON

9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16

ME A Taitono

16 17 18 19 20 21 22 23 24

V IV# III I Taitono

24 25 26 27 28 29 30 31 32

III V IV# I V I Taitono Taitono

32 33 34 35 36 37 38 39 40

The image shows a handwritten musical score for guitar. It consists of a single staff with a treble clef and a key signature of one sharp (F#). The title is "BELLA FIGLIOLA CA VENI CO MEA". The score is divided into measures numbered 0 to 40. Above the staff, fret numbers are indicated for each measure. Chord diagrams are written above the staff, and the lyrics are written below. There are two "Taitono" markings, which likely indicate a specific playing technique or a section of the piece. The score ends at measure 40.

fig.3

1.2

COTTANELLESE

A

CHI VO-LE PRE-NDE TO-GLIA CO-TA-NE-LLA CI VO-MO CE-NTA SCU-DI

DI-G-RO-LLA *glm.* CI VO-MO CE-NTA SCU-DI DI CO-RO-LLA

CE-NTA CI-NQUA-TA DE FA RE I'A-NE-LLA *glm.*

glm.

Detailed description: The image shows a handwritten musical score for a piece titled 'COTTANELLESE'. It consists of three systems of music, each with a vocal line and a piano accompaniment line. The first system is marked with a large 'A'. The lyrics are written below the vocal line. The second system includes performance markings '4'' and '2'' above the notes, and 'glm.' below. The third system also includes '4'' and '2'' markings and 'glm.' below. The piano accompaniment is written in a simple, rhythmic style with many beamed notes.

2

3

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8

V V IV* III IV* V III

E NON CI PO TE VINA - A - A - A - SCE TA - NTO SE -

9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16

II V IV# III III I

- LO E SE NON VOLEVI SE - E - GI -

TUTTO

17 18 19 20 21 22 23 24

- TA L'ALTO - RE SE -

SE NON VOLEVI SE -

fig.4

FRONNE DEI
CARCEDATI

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8

FRONNE E - ELI - HO 0-0

8 9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16

CHIE - STIA A PAO - NNE DEI CA - A - AR - C ERA -

16 17 18 19 20 21 22 23 24

CHI - LL DIE SE E

24 25 26 27 28 29 30 31 32

E - E - E E CHI | L' DO PA MI LI A

33 34 35

The image shows a handwritten musical score on ten staves. The title 'FRONNE DEI CARCEDATI' is written at the top. The score is divided into measures, with measure numbers 0 through 35 indicated below the staves. The music is written in a single system with a treble clef and a key signature of one sharp (F#). The lyrics are written below the notes. The score ends with a double bar line at measure 35.

fig. 5

GUARDA CU VENA

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8

V VI VI# V IV III

A DA BELLA MA BO - TTA D'A - A - EQUA

tritono

8 9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16

VI V II III II I

A DA BELLA STARRA MI - I - IA

16 17 18 19 20 21 22 23 24

A

II III IV VI III II I

E DA - CCI MA BO - TTE D'A - A - EQUA

24 25 26 27 28 29 30 31 32

HE LO HE LO HE LO

32 33 34 35 36 37 38 39 40

HI I I I A

40 41 42 43 44 45 46 47 48

A I

fig.7

| LAMENTO FUNEBRE |
MARTANO

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8
A HA - GGHU - MPANA - TU CA FA SI VI HA - GGHU

9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16
I IV# I
B MPA-RATU CA FA CASE LA FE-STA NO VENIA
| TRITONO | | TRITONO |

17 18 19 20 21 22 23 24
IV# I II VI IV
CA SE LA FE-STA NO VE-NIA AU SA-PU-TUCA SCETTI LA CRI-ME
| TRITONO |

fig.8

MIE TETE
MIE TITOLI

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8

MIE TETE MIE-TI-TO-O-O-LI A-BBA-SSO È A-TTO RNO

9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16

-O-O-O-O-O CHE LE CU PE LCE
FRAGMENTO A FRAGMENTO B

16 17 18 19 20 21 22 23 24

CHE LE CU PE - LE PE L LLO

24 25 26 27 28 29 30 31 32

CHÉ LE CU PE LLE PE LLO O-O-O TA-

32 33 34 35 36 37 38 39 40

SUB VANO

fig.9

ITALIA RANALDI
NINNA NANNA

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8

V

FA - TIE LA NA - NNA

VI VI# VII

FI - GGHIUHE - O CHE NO
FRANZESCO

8 9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16

III

- TIE

III VI 4 IV

LE PE - CO - RE - LIE

16 17 18 19 20 21 22 23 24

V III II I

SO - O RIENTRA - TE TU TIE

fig. 10

| NINÓ NINÓ NINÓ |

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8

♩ V IV# VI IV# III VI#

Ni - NÓ NI NÓ NI NÓ | TRITONO |

A B

9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16

♩ V IV# IV# VI V

| TRITONO | B | TRITONO

A A

CANTO DEGLI
SPACCAPIETRE

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8

♩ E HA-NA HA HA LU CA ZZA - TO - O - RE

8 9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16

♩ E QUANTO BENE QUANTO BE-NE MI VO-L'A

16 17 18 19 20 21 22 23 24

♩ ME

fig. 11

STORNELLI ALLA
BAROZZARA

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8

9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16

17 18 19 20 21 22 23 24

fig. 12

STORNELLI AL MODO
DEI MIETTORI

1

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8

V III IV V

E LO MIO ANORE STA IN CA - A - A - TRA

8 9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16

V III II V IV VI^b IV

GNA A ME TE E E NE LE RE PO-R TA LE ME -

[TRITONO]

16 17 18 19 20 21 22 23 24

IV IV III II I

E - E - LE NO-SCA-TE

fig. 14

| STORNELLI A
SERENATA |

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8

I II I II

SE-IL PA-PA ME DO NA- A SSE- È ME - ZZA

9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16

III II#6 III II IV

RO - O - MA - A - A E ME DI - CE

| Tra Tomo |
FRAGMENTO

16 17 18 19 20 21 22 23 24

II II III II III II I

SSE RA - A - SCIA - A NNA CHI - i T'A - A VA - A

24 25 26 27 28 29 30 31 32

fig. 15

Pizzica tarantata

racc.62 n.1 Annabella Rossi

Luigi Stifani

The musical score is written in 4/4 time and consists of five staves of music. The first staff begins with a rest followed by a quarter note G4, then a series of eighth notes: A4, B4, C5, B4, A4, G4, F4, E4, D4, C4. A triplet of eighth notes (D4, E4, F4) is marked with a '3' below it. The second staff starts at measure 5 and contains a triplet of eighth notes (G4, A4, B4) marked with a '3' below it, followed by a quarter note C5, then a quarter note B4, and a quarter note A4. A bracket above the staff from measure 7 to 8 is labeled 'passaggio non comprensibile'. The third staff starts at measure 9 and contains a triplet of eighth notes (G4, A4, B4) marked with a '3' below it, followed by a quarter note C5, then a quarter note B4, and a quarter note A4. The fourth staff starts at measure 15 and contains a quarter note G4, a quarter note F4, a quarter note E4, and a quarter note D4. A bracket below the staff from measure 16 to 17 is labeled 'tritono'. The fifth staff starts at measure 21 and contains a quarter note G4, a quarter note F4, a quarter note E4, and a quarter note D4. A bracket below the staff from measure 22 to 23 is labeled 'tritono'. The score ends with a double bar line.

fig. 16

TROPARIUM BENEDICT.
EUCARISTICA

Handwritten musical score for Troparium Benedict. Eucaristica, measures 1-32. The score is written on a single staff in treble clef. The title is written in a box at the top. The measures are numbered 1 through 32. The notation includes notes, rests, and fingerings. Roman numerals (I, II, III, IV) are used to indicate fingerings for certain notes. A key signature of one sharp (F#) is indicated by a sharp sign on the F line of the staff at measure 16. The score ends with a double bar line at measure 32.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8

8 9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16

16 17 18 19 20 21 22 23 24

24 25 26 27 28 29 30 31 32

fig. 20

Canto della Campagna Romana (G. Nataletti)

V VII- VI+ V I 3

2 3

fig. 22

Da Piccolo Fanciullo - Rec Sandro Portelli

Fig.23

Trasc: CLAUDIO
HERICO

Aut: A. Ricci (92)
(MASOCCIA)

CANTO A
OLI OLEDDA

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

10 11 12 13 14 15 16 17 18

19 20 21 22 23 24 25 26 27

28 29 30 31 32 33 34 35 36

37 38 39 40 41 42 43 44 45 46 47 48 49 50 51 52 53 54

V IV#5

II IIIb

CODICIA

I (Tutto I-IV# 5+6 Cant)

II IV#b

Cant

Handwritten musical score for two staves, measures 40-52. The score is organized into four systems, each with two staves (labeled 1 and 2) and a brace on the right. Roman numerals are written above the first staff of each system. Measure numbers are written below the staves.

- System 1 (Measures 40-47):** Roman numerals: $\text{IV} \downarrow$, $\text{III} \downarrow$, II , $\text{IV} = \text{V}$. Measure numbers: 40, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46, 47.
- System 2 (Measures 48-54):** Roman numerals: $\text{IV} \downarrow$, $\text{III} \downarrow$, I . Measure numbers: 48, 49, 50, 51, 52, 53, 54.
- System 3 (Measures 55-62):** Roman numerals: $\text{IV} \downarrow$, $\text{III} \downarrow$, I . Measure numbers: 55, 56, 57, 58, 59, 60, 61, 62.
- System 4 (Measures 63-70):** Roman numerals: IV , III , I . Measure numbers: 63, 64, 65, 66, 67, 68, 69, 70.

Handwritten musical notation for the first system, measures 121-137. The system consists of two staves, labeled 1 and 2, with a brace on the left. Measure numbers 121, 122, 123, 124, 125, 126, 127, 128, and 129 are written below the staves. Above measures 124, 125, and 126, there are handwritten markings: $\text{III} \downarrow$, $\text{III} \downarrow$, and $\text{III} \downarrow$ respectively. The notation includes various note values and rests.

Handwritten musical notation for the second system, measures 138-146. The system consists of two staves, labeled 1 and 2, with a brace on the left. Measure numbers 138, 139, 140, 141, 142, 143, 144, 145, and 146 are written below the staves. The notation includes various note values and rests.

Handwritten musical notation for the third system, measures 147-148. The system consists of two staves, labeled 1 and 2, with a brace on the left. Measure numbers 147 and 148 are written below the staves. The notation includes various note values and rests.

Empty musical staves for the remainder of the page, consisting of ten systems of two staves each.

Fig. 24

INNANANNA LOITAX SAIBITO!

The image shows a handwritten musical score on a page with five staves. The title 'INNANANNA LOITAX SAIBITO!' is written in a box at the top. The first staff contains a sequence of notes with Roman numerals II, II, and I above them, and fingerings 16, 14, 13, 14, 15, 16 below. The second staff contains notes with Roman numerals II, II, and I above them, and fingerings 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22 below. The third staff contains notes with Roman numerals II, II, and I above them, and fingerings 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28 below. The fourth staff contains notes with Roman numerals II, II, and I above them, and fingerings 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34 below. The fifth staff contains notes with Roman numerals II, II, and I above them, and fingerings 35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40 below. The score includes various musical notations such as beams, slurs, and accents. Handwritten annotations include 'Tritono = 564, 10' and 'II - III = 248c' on the second staff, and 'Tritono = 654 c' and 'II - III = 246 c' on the third staff.

Tritono = 564, 10
II - III = 248c

Tritono = 654 c
II - III = 246 c

SITOGRAFIA

Cd / Vinili

Canzoni popolari del Lazio/Folk Song of Lazio, CD

https://youtube.com/playlist?list=OLAK5uy_mIEUGjX6HGc28Uml_6dwrLLYKwYGlyoFQ&si=gakw2TUfLrez7zji

Italia - Le Stagioni Degli Anni '70 - I Dischi Del Sole, LP, Album, Gatefold - 1971 CD

link: <https://youtu.be/0ErbKclW2Gk?si=XISQrLC7jor2xE0F>

Il Lazio vol.2, i canti e le zampogne, Albatros documenti originali del folklore europeo, Editoriale Sciascia, 1976, (Vinile)

CD - Canto d'amore - Voci, suoni e ritmi della Grecia Salentina a cura di Luigi Chiriatti e Roberto Raheli, Aramirè

Brani trascritti

Stornelli a serenata, Italia Ranaldi:

<https://youtu.be/RKytC7IDYkQ?si=0W7JI1CobUB4WtE>

Stornelli al modo dei mietitori, Italia Ranaldi:

<https://youtu.be/KsMbFXC40Mk?si=AtX6Wt4DClu0O7Lv>

Stornelli di mietitura a Montasola:

<https://youtu.be/YAKkQDDINnQ?si=1K2YxijfrB-nBp8z>

Ninna nanna, Italia Ranaldi:

<https://youtu.be/XSOluJ7gHto?si=s3N1REkoqzCvfhpb>

A montasola, discanto sabino alla "montasolina"

<https://youtu.be/LNdYjDuMhtg?si=XxyQcew9Pk19Ev0s>

Stornelli alla Barozzara di Contigliano, Rieti. Teche Rai Lazio, Rieti n.37

<https://www.teche.rai.it/2014/11/archivio-del-folklore-musicale-italiano-lazio/>

Stornelli a recchione di Selci, Rieti. Teche Rai Lazio, Rieti n.40

<https://www.teche.rai.it/2014/11/archivio-del-folklore-musicale-italiano-lazio/>

Mietete mietitori, Anticoli Corrado, Archivio De Carolis

Guarda cu vena, stornelli calabresi, Cd 11 G.Marini

Fronne del carcere (NA) Cd didattico n.12, G.Marini

Bella figliola che vieni co mea, racc. 087 A n.16

https://bibliomediateca.santacecilia.it/bibliomediateca/cms.view?munu_str=0_1_0_5&numDoc=21&physDoc=7525&pflag=personalizationFindEtnomusicologia&level=brano

Ninna Nanna Lomax:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DF7vitN9v9g&list=PLT33L30yCPdKhtGlqy1av-1qe4ROnOTKj&index=14>

Ninò, Ninò, Ninò, racc. 024 B, n.12 Martano (Le)

https://bibliomediateca.santacecilia.it/bibliomediateca/cms.view?menu_str=0_1_0_5&numDoc=21&physDoc=1294&pflag=personalizationFindEtnomusicologia&level=brano

Lamenti funebri di Martano, racc. 024 B doc. n.08, 010

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Pizzica Tarantata di Luigi Stifani, racc. 062 n.1

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Canto degli spaccapietre, racc. 24b n.21

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Tropàion della benedizione eucaristica racc. 20 n.96

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Inno che sostituisce il Cheruvikòn il Santo e grande Sabato, racc. 020, n. 35

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Archivi online

Archivio Nazionale S.Cecilia online:

https://bibliomediateca.santacecilia.it/bibliomediateca/cms.view?menu_str=0_1_0_5&numDoc=21

Teche Rai, archivio del folklore italiano:

<https://www.teche.rai.it/archivio-del-folklore-italiano/>

Archivio Alfredo Majorano:

<https://www.internetculturale.it/it/41/collezioni-digitali/26306/archivio-sonoro-alfredo-majorano>

Articoli online

Crickmore, L. (2012). *A Musicological Interpretation of the Akkadian Term SIḪPU*. *Journal of Cuneiform Studies*, 64, 57-64. Stable URL: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.5615/jcunestud.64.0057>

Valentina Voto, *Inni delfici di Apollo*, due trascrizioni

https://www.academia.edu/36296343/GLI_INNI_DELFICI_AD_APOLLO_DUE_ISCRIZIONI_CON_NOTAZIONE_MUSICALE

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Altre evidenze in archivi sonori

Teche Rai, Umbria, Perugia: Documento n. 14 Maltignano di Cascia

Teche Rai, Umbria, Terni¹:

n. 6 “*Mietitura alla nostrale*” Vallecupa Arrone,

n. 12 “*Canzone del Maggio*” S. Lucia Stroncone,

n. 21 “*Ottava Rima*” Vallecupa Arrone

Archivio Nazionale Santa Cecilia²

Raccolta n. 37 di Carpitella a Terni: Doc. n.30, n.41, n.42, n.43, n.45, n.51, n.53, n.54, n.71

Teche Rai Abruzzo, L'Aquila: n. 1 “*Canto di Mietitura*” Pescina

Napoli - Archivio S.Cecilia

Raccolta 087 : n. 4 e 7 di San Giuseppe Vesuviano.

Raccolta 120 D : n.1, n.5

Raccolta 136-I : n. 90 e 94 Somma Vesuviana tammurriata pellegrinaggio, n. 101 festa pellegrinaggio tammurriata di Biaggiola e Carpitella a Somma Vesuviana.

Salento - Archivio S.Cecilia:

Raccolta 024 B di Lomax:

n.114 Fimmene fimmene Calimera,

¹ Teche Rai Umbria: <https://www.teche.rai.it/2014/11/archivio-del-folklore-musicale-italiano-umbria/>

² https://bibliomediateca.santacecilia.it/bibliomediateca/cms.view?munu_str=0_1_0_5&numDoc=21

- n.129 Galatone ninna nanna,
- n.131 ninna nanna Galatone,
- n.132 filastrocche infantili Galatone,
- n.133 Galatone lamento funebre,
- n.134 lamento funebre Galatone.

Raccolta Carpitella, De Martino 48

- n.13 pizzica taranta Nardo,
- n.14 Nardo tarantismo,
- n.15 Nardo tarantismo,
- n.17 lamento funebre Nardo

Raccolta Carpitella 53

- n.3 Pizzica tarantata,
- n.10 Sanarica Lecce.

Ruffano nella raccolta 55

- n.2 Tarantella danza Ruffano,
- n.3 Ruffano danze.

Piana degli albanesi (Palermo) - Archivio S.Cecilia:

Raccolta 020 di Ottavio Tiby:

- n.130, 140, 143, 145, 146, 147, 180, 182, 184, 185, 186

